

Investigating the Role of Resilience as a Mediator in the Link between Internet Addiction and Anxiety

Halenur Kutuk

Istanbul Esenyurt University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Child Development, Istanbul, Türkiye

Abstract

Problematic internet use has become one of the most important problems of our age with the development of technology. Individuals may experience some psychological problems due to their internet usage habits. One of these problems is anxiety. The aim of this research is to reveal the effect of psychological resilience on the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety. For this purpose, data collected from 338 Turkish individuals was tested with mediation analysis (age range = 21–65 years). The findings showed that there were significant relationships between internet addiction, anxiety, and resilience. In addition, resilience was found to be a full mediator in the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety. The results were interpreted and discussed in light of the literature.

Keywords: Internet addiction, anxiety, resilience

INTRODUCTION

Anxiety, which was first defined by Freud as a function of the ego, generally refers to the reflection of fear arising from danger as uneasiness or irrational fear in humans (Budak, 2000; Manav, 2011;). Pathological anxiety can be mentioned if the individual is constantly experiencing anxiety, cannot prevent this situation, and it negatively affects the individual's life (Çoban & Karaman, 2013). When the factors that may cause anxiety are eliminated and the distress experienced by the individual decreases or disappears, this anxiety situation is considered normal (Ülev, 2014). It is stated that the main reason for anxiety is that the individual does not trust herself or himself enough and cannot develop a positive self (Çevik, 2006). Sargın (1990) argues that this situation may result from one's childhood experiences. Cüceloğlu (1999), on the other hand, lists the causes of anxiety as the withdrawal of support from the individual, waiting for the result when it is known that a negative result will occur, the person experiencing internal conflict, and being in uncertainty. In the study of Alisianoğlu and Ulutaş (2000), it was revealed that age, gender, parental attitudes, parental education level, income status, and number of siblings are among the factors causing anxiety. In addition, it is stated in the study that the rapid development of technology and its problematic use cause anxiety. With the change in lifestyle and the use of intense digital tools, technology addictions have started to increase (Rugai & Hamilton-Ekeke, 2016). Uncontrolled use of rapidly developing technology causes some addictions in individuals. It is stated that internet addiction, which is one of these addiction types, has a strong relationship with anxiety (Li et al., 2019; Laconi et al., 2014; Ostovar et al., 2016; Younes et al., 2016). In the study of Romdhane et al. (2023), it was determined that intense digital tool use and problematic internet use were associated with anxiety. In the study of Harman et al. (2005), it was revealed that spending too much time on the internet increases anxiety. Akboğa and Gürgan (2019) also stated in their research that problematic internet use affects anxiety. Based on these studies, it is thought that internet addiction may be one of the indicators of anxiety.

With the development of technology in the 21st century, the use of the internet has become increasingly widespread. The use of the internet, which has been increasing rapidly around the world, provides great convenience in the lives of individuals. The internet can be defined as a mass communication tool where individuals can store, share, and easily access their information. People often use the internet to have a pleasant time or to meet their various needs (Anderson, 2001). There are studies showing that the number of internet users in the world is more than 4 billion (We Are Social, 2020; Worldometers, 2019).

Corresponding Author

Halenur Kütük, Istanbul Esenyurt University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Child Development, Istanbul, Turkey

E-mail: halenuroluckutuk@esenyurt.edu.tr

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Although there are many aspects of the internet that make our lives easier, unconscious, uncontrolled, and malicious use can cause various physiological and psychological problems in individuals.

Addictive behaviour is one of the most important psychological problems that the internet can cause. Addiction is defined as an individual's loss of control over any substance or behaviour (Yeşilay, 2023). Although the first issues that come to mind about addiction are alcohol, cigarettes, or drugs, behavioural addictions, including internet addiction, should not be ignored. So much so that Christakis (2010) describes internet addiction as the epidemic of the 21st century. Pan et al. (2020) state that approximately 7% of the world's population has problems with problematic internet use. The concept of internet addiction is expressed as more problematic internet use today. Griffiths (2005) stated that the increase in internet use may cause an addiction that shares similar mechanisms with alcohol or drug addictions. The issue of addiction, which may be a result of internet use, has frequently come up in studies conducted in the literature (Brezing et al., 2010; Widyanto & Griffiths, 2006; Young, 1996). Internet addiction, also known as problematic internet use, is a problem that can cause serious negative consequences, including loss of control and obsessive behaviours (Dufour et al., 2019; Weinstein & Aboujaoude, 2015). Studies on the issues that may result from problematic internet use emphasize academic issues, family issues, friendship difficulties, physical and mental health issues (Alimoradi et al., 2019; Özparlak & Karakaya, 2020). Müller et al. (2014) reported that individuals with problematic internet use experience intense psychological distress. In a similar study, Kim et al. (2016) stated that problematic internet use may increase thoughts about suicide. When the relevant literature is examined, it is seen that problematic internet use especially causes anxiety problems (Bozkurt et al., 2013; Ho et al., 2014; Van Den Eijnden et al., 2018). Considering all these negative consequences of problematic internet use, it may play a role in increasing the individual's anxiety level.

Resilience as a mediator

Resilience is defined as an important protective factor against online risks that can offset the negative psychological consequences of both problematic internet use and exposure to online hazards (Wisniewski & ark, 2015). Resilience is the positive process that a person goes through, based on both psychological and social, environmental, and biological factors, in order to protect her mental health despite going through a difficult process at any time in her or his life (Tsirigotis & Luczak, 2018). In other words, while it covers concepts such as resilience, adapting to change, and being flexible, it also expresses the ability of the individual to cope with the problem thanks to these characteristics (Fletcher & Sarkar, 2013). Individuals with high resilience do not prefer avoidance strategies and instead use approach strategies such as problem solving and planning when they encounter stressful events. This ensures that individuals experience less stress and encounter less discomfort. In addition, resilience is seen as an important

factor in protecting individuals from addiction (Klag & Bradley, 2004; Kodoman & Eker, 2019).

When the literature is examined, it is seen that there is a negative relationship between problematic internet use and resilience. It was stated that problematic internet use increased due to low resilience (Duygun, 2017; Jin et al., 2019; Nam et al., 2019; Robertson et al., 2018; Taş, 2019; Wang, 2022; Zhou et al., 2017). In studies examining the relationship between anxiety resulting from problematic internet use and resilience, it has been stated that resilience is a protective factor against stress, anxiety, and negative affect (Campbell et al., 2005; Eschleman et al., 2010; Lara Cabrera et al., 2021; Ye et al., 2020). According to Demirsu's (2018) study of university students, the level of resilience rose along with the students' low levels of anxiety. In the study conducted by Salah et al. (2021) with 3816 individuals from 94 countries, it was stated that the feelings of anxiety decreased as the resilience of the individuals increased.

When all these studies were examined, no study dealt with the relationship between anxiety, resilience, and internet addiction. The aim of the study is to reveal the role of resilience in the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety. It is possible to say that resilience is a variable that is good for anxiety. For this reason, it is expected that addicts will be able to keep their anxiety levels under control by increasing their resilience.

METHODS

Participant and Procedure

This study was designed as a cross-sectional study. Convenience sampling method was preferred as the sampling method. The participants of the study consisted of 179 female (53%) and 159 male (47%) individuals living in Istanbul, the largest city in Türkiye. The sample's mean age is 37.25 (SD = 8.61; age range = 21 to 65 years). The majority of the participants (43.5%) have a very high socioeconomic status. Detailed information on the demographic information of the participants is given in Table 1. Data were collected on a voluntary basis. Before participating in the research, they were informed about the research and no fee was paid. Participants were informed that they could withdraw from the study at any stage they wished. Finally, the Declaration of Helsinki was followed at all stages of the study.

Measures

Young Internet Addiction Scale (YIAS)

It was developed by Pawlikowski et al. (2013) to measure individuals' internet addiction levels. It was adapted into Turkish by Kutlu et al. (2016). The scale, which consists of 12 items, is answered in a 5-point Likert type (1=Strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree). High scores from the scale indicate a high level of internet addiction. It can be said that the reliability (Cronbach alpha: 0.91) and validity ($\chi^2 = 144.93$, $df = 52$,

RMSEA = 0.072, RMR = 0.70, GFI = 0.93, AGFI = 0.90, CFI=0.95 and IFI=0.91) of the scale are in the acceptable range.

Table 1: Participants' descriptive

Variable	Frequency	%
<i>Gender</i>		
Female	179	53
Male	159	47
<i>Socio-economic status</i>		
Low	7	2.1
Medium	66	19.15
High	118	34.9
Very High	147	43.5
<i>Education level</i>		
Primary school	14	4.1
Middle school	29	8.6
High school	84	24.9
Undergraduate	179	53
Graduate	32	9.4
<i>Marital status</i>		
Divorced	165	48.8
Married	173	51.2

Brief Resilience Scale(BRS)

The scale used to measure the psychological resilience of individuals was developed by Smith et al. (2008). It was adapted into Turkish by Doğan (2015). The scale, which consists of 6 items, is answered in a 5-point Likert type (1=Strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree). High scores on the scale indicate a high level of resilience. It can be said that the reliability (Cronbach alpha: 0.83) and validity (CFA: $\chi^2/df = 1.83$, NFI = 0.99, NNFI = 0.99, CFI = 0.99, IFI = 0.99, RFI = 0.97, GFI = 0.99, AGFI = 0.96, RMSEA = 0.05, and SRMR = 0.03) of the scale are in the acceptable range.

Beck Anxiety Scale (BAS)

It was developed by Beck (1988) to measure the anxiety levels experienced by individuals. It was adapted into Turkish by Ulusoy et al. (1998). The scale, which consists of 21 items, is answered in a 4-point Likert type (0 = none and 3 = severely). High scores on the scale indicate high levels of anxiety. It can be said that the reliability (Cronbach alpha: 0.83) values of the scale are in the acceptable range.

Statistical Analysis

Within the scope of the research, firstly, some preliminary analyzes were made. Within the scope of preliminary analysis, missing and outlier values were removed from the data set. Descriptive statistics of the variables were calculated. It was observed that the skewness and kurtosis values of the variables

were between ± 1.5 and the normality assumption was met (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2012). After the preliminary analysis, the remaining data were analyzed with PROCESS v4.2 model 4 developed by Hayes (2018). The significance of the mediator variable whose effect was revealed by the model was calculated with the 5,000 bootstrapping method at a 95% confidence interval. The absence of a zero value between the highest and lowest confidence intervals obtained as a result of the bootstrapping method means that the mediating variables are statistically significant (Gürbüz, 2019).

RESULTS

Correlation analysis indicated (see Table 2) that anxiety was positively correlated with both resilience, and internet addiction. There were also positive correlation between internet addiction, and resilience. The reliability coefficients of all variables were at an acceptable level. Skewness and kurtosis values were within the normality criteria.

Mediation Analysis

The data were analyzed using SPSS 24 and the SPSS macro program PROCESS v4.2 model 4 by Hayes (2018). The findings revealed that internet addiction significantly and positively predicted resilience ($B = -.322, p < .001$). Resilience significantly and positively predicted anxiety ($\beta = -.261, p < .001$). The results of the mediation analysis are presented in Table 3 and Figure 1.

The mediation analysis revealed a statistically significant indirect association between internet addiction and anxiety, mediated by resilience ($\beta = -.252, SE = .203, 95\% CI = -1.31, -.52$). When resilience, which was suggested as a mediator variable, was included in the analysis, it was seen that the effect of internet addiction (predictive variable) on anxiety disappeared completely and it was no longer a significant predictor of anxiety ($\beta = .027, p > .05$). According to Baron and Kenny (1986), the disappearance of the effect of the predictor variable indicates that resilience has a "full mediating role" in the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety.

Figure 1. The result of mediational model

Bootstrap analysis was performed to test the significance of the mediating role of the resilience variable. Thanks to the bootstrap analysis, the significance level of the indirect effect (a.b) can be determined (MacKinnon et al., 2004). In order to determine the significance of the mediating role in this study,

Table 2: Descriptive statistics, reliabilities and correlations for the study variables

Variable	Descriptive Statistics and Reliabilities					Correlations	
	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	α	1	2
1. Anxiety	13.93	12.61	1.07	.17	.897	–	
2. Internet Addiction	23.52	8.47	.72	-.21	.93	-.11*	–
3. Resilience	18.61	3.46	-.35	1.13	.72	-.26**	-.32**

Note. ** $p < .01$, * $p < .05$

the bootstrap value (number of resamples) was taken as 5000. In the bootstrap analysis performed to determine the significance of the full mediating role of resilience in the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety, it was determined that there was no zero (0) value between the lower and upper limits in the 95% confidence interval. According to the result obtained thanks to this data, it was seen that the coercive conflict action style had a full mediator role in a meaningful way (%95 CI [.06, .18]).

DISCUSSION

In this study, the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety and the mediating role of resilience in this relationship were examined. The findings are discussed below in light of the literature, respectively.

The first finding of the study is that there is a positive and significant relationship between internet addiction and anxiety. The reason for this relationship may be the emergence of anxiety in the case of not being able to access the internet. Studies in the literature also support our findings. There are studies showing that there is a positive relationship between internet addiction and anxiety (Azher et al., 2014; Gholamian et al., 2017; Göldağ, 2017; Younes et al., 2016). Studies have shown that the higher the internet addiction, the higher the level of anxiety. Contrary to our findings, Javaeed et al. (2019) did not find a relationship between internet addiction and anxiety in their study.

As the second finding of the study, a negative relationship was found between internet addiction and resilience. The reason for this may be that individuals with a high level of resilience have positive thoughts, are social individuals around them, and have

characteristics such as being harmonious. In addition, it is thought that these features will protect the individual from the risk of internet addiction, like other addictions. Studies with consistent results with ours are available in the literature. Studies that found a negative relationship between internet addiction and resilience support our research (Cao et al., 2020; Robertson et al., 2018). Studies reveal that resilience plays a preventive role in internet addiction (Nam et al., 2018; Wisniewski et al., 2015). These findings also show parallels with the results of our study.

The third and main finding of the study is that when resilience is included in the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety, the effect of internet addiction disappears. This finding reveals that resilience plays a full mediating role in the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety. This may be due to the fact that resilience is a protective factor. Resilience is seen as one of the most important concepts in coping with anxiety. It is stated that the high level of resilience in an individual enables better coping with adverse situations (Yi et al., 2020; Öz & Yılmaz, 2009; Sill et al., 2006). When we look at the studies examining the relationship between resilience and anxiety in the literature, it is seen that individuals with weak resilience levels are more affected by the events and situations they experience (Bravilovskaia et al., 2018). It was observed that when these individuals received resilience training, their anxiety levels decreased (Sood et al., 2011; Schiraldi et al., 2010). Poole et al. (2017) found that resilience is associated with anxiety symptoms in their study. This finding also supports our study. It is thought that resilience is a highly effective variable in the concept of anxiety, as individuals' levels of resilience determine the level of anxiety and how it arises (Smith & Yang, 2017).

Table 3: Results of the mediation analysis

Path	Coefficient	95%CI	
		LL	UL
Internet Addiction → Resilience	-.322	-.170	-.090
Internet Addiction → Resilience → Anxiety	-.252	-1.318	-.520
Total effect	.162	.003	.320
Direct effect	.041	-.122	.204
Total indirect effect	.121	.060	.189

Note. CI confidence interval; LL lower limit; UL upper limit

Implications

Internet addiction is one of the concepts that can deeply affect an individual's daily life. In particular, taking a role that increases anxiety in the individual can make internet addiction more dangerous. The individual may experience mental health problems due to this problem. From this point of view, eliminating the effect of internet addiction on anxiety can be an important step in supporting the mental health of individuals. Based on the findings, it can be said that resilience can eliminate this relationship between internet addiction and anxiety. In other words, if the resilience of internet-addicted individuals improves, they can expect to experience fewer anxiety problems. Based on this reality, training programs and applications that support the resilience of internet-addicted individuals can be a solution to anxiety problems. Because increasing the level of resilience of the individual by participating in these training activities can help them cope with anxiety more easily, increasing training programs aimed at increasing resilience can indirectly help individuals achieve various gains.

Conclusion

As a result, it has been revealed that resilience has a full mediator role in the relationship between internet addiction and anxiety. In addition, the direct relationships between internet addiction, anxiety, and resilience variables are also mentioned. Within the findings, it can be said that the participation of individuals with internet addiction in practices that will improve their resilience will positively affect their anxiety levels. For this reason, it is recommended that individuals with internet addiction be included in such practices. The inclusion of individuals in practices that will increase their resilience will make serious contributions to the person in the spiritual sense.

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Pre-registration Statement. This study was not pre-registered.

Ethical Approval. The study was performed in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki and its following updates.

Consent to Participate. Informed consent was obtained from all the individual participants that were included in the study.

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